

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Relationship Between Temperature and Energy Consumption in Europe

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	28/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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Project details

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End date	31/01/2025

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
DOI	digital object identifier

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Research Data	Structured text, Images, Source code	CSV, text/python, image/png	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Research Data":

Contains spreadsheets with the raw data and processed data in csv format, the source code used for data processing and visualizing as plaintext python files, and pictures of produced graphs in PNG format.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Energy Efficiency (nrg_ind_eff)	https://doi.org/10.2908/NRG_I_ND_EFF	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	ERA5-Land monthly averaged data from 1950 to present	https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.68d2bb30	CC BY 4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The existing datasets will be preprocessed to ensure compatibility with subsequent analyses. Data handling will be done using Python and commonly used scientific libraries (such as pandas, NumPy, and SciPy). Established statistical methods will be used to analyze the data. The results will be provided in open machine readable format, primarily CSV. Key results will additionally be visualized using appropriate graphs using common libraries (such as Matplotlib and Plotly).

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in *File_Naming_Conventions.pdf*. Data files include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated using Git.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Documentation will be provided in the README file and will make the workflow transparent and reproducible. This includes a description of all preprocessing steps, analytical methods, and statistical techniques applied during the project. Python scripts used for data cleaning, transformation, and analysis will be made available, along with information on software versions and library dependencies. These materials will enable others to validate the results, replicate the workflow, or adapt it for their own use.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data and data entry validation.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Martin Folzberger (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Research Data) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The rights to control access to all datasets will lie with the Data Manager, who was identified earlier in the document.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2026-02-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI 10.70124/cd0p3-gv967	CC-BY-4.0 for data and images MIT for code

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The processed and published data will be made available in open, non-proprietary formats such as CSV to allow user to open and analyze the files with common open tools. No proprietary or domain-specific software will be required, however, users wishing to replicate the full analysis pipeline may need require some standard scientific Python libraries. All required dependencies and code used during the project will be documented to support reproducibility.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	<p>The primary audience are members of the scientific community, specifically researchers in the fields of energy systems, environmental sciences, sustainability studies.</p> <p>The data may also be of interest to policymakers, urban planners, and utility companies, as it can support evidence-based decision-making related to energy efficiency measures and demand forecasting.</p>

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.